

Article	Title	Author(s)	Page
16	Undergraduates' Perception of Factors Influencing Career Development and Choice: Implications for Counselling	Omotosho, J.A., Ph.D.	77
17	Improving the Quality of Teaching and Learning of Elementary Science through a Resourceful Environment	Olagunju, A.M., Ph.D.	84
18	Internet Connectivity Vis A Vis Prospect and Problems on Research Growth in Academic Institutions in Nigeria	Osunrinde, A.A., Adekiya, I.S. & Adeyemo, K.A.	90
19	The Relationship between Principal Managerial Task Performance and Secondary School Students Academic Performance	Martins Fabunmi Ph.D. & Olabisi Adejoke Sheyin Ph.D.	92
20	A Comparative Study of The Perceived Effect of Democratic and Autocratic Leadership Styles on Job Performance	Olurotimi Samson Akinyele	99
21	Interpersonal Attraction, Group Activities and Coach-Leadership Style as Correlates of Team Performance	Ajayi, M.A., Ph.D. & Sunday Ogunleye	102
22	The Influence of Pubertal Timing on the Social Self-Image of School going Female Adolescents in Nigeria.	Alfred A. Adegoke. Ph.D. & A.P. Aboyeji, MBBS, FWACS	106
23	Understanding the Family Structure through Networking in the African Setting: The Case of Nigeria.	Oyewo B.A.	111
24	Socio-Demographic Factors involved in Health Care Service Utilization among People in Ibadan North Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria.	Babatunde, S.O. Ph.D.	114
25	Level of Awareness of Graduating Degree and Diploma Students' on Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS)	Babalola, J.F. Ph.D. & Fadoju, A.O. Ph.D.	119
26	A Report of Home for the Aged in America: Implications for the Year 2025's United Nation's Projection of Nigeria	Asagba, R. B. Ph.D.	124
27	Information Technology: A Vital Tool for Family Planning Communication	Igbafe Modupe Aruaye	132
28	The Relevance of Information and Communication Technology in Research Works: The Case Study of Higher Institutions in Nigeria	Osunrinde, A.A.	136
29	Preliminary Exercise as Safety Value in the Participation of Sporting Activities	Ajayi, R.O. Ph.D.	139
30	Financial House as a Tool for Alleviating Poverty in Nigeria	Adu, E. Olusola. Ph.D. & Ayeni, A. O.	143

INTERNET CONNECTIVITY VIS A VIS PROSPECT AND PROBLEMS ON RESEARCH
GROWTH IN ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS IN NIGERIA

BY

OSUNRINDE, A.A., ADEKIYA, I.S. & ADEYEMO, K.A.

OSUN STATE COLLEGE OF TECHNOLOGY, ESA-OKE

ABSTRACT

The main theme of this paper is to examine information technology In various perspectives. The authors try to look at the importance of information technology in relation to research works and finally identify some problems facing information technology through research activities.

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, there has been a progressive tilt towards the adoption of technology not only to support the data transmission in various formats but also to ensure the security and reliability of information flow from the origin to the end users without undue interruptions.

Generally speaking, some segments of society, especially the educational sectors to other numerous categories have engaged in different nodes of electronic transfer of data and access locally or internationally through Local Area Networks (LAN) and Wide Area Network (WAN). Both net works are more relevant mainly because there can be an interconnection of data base from different locations which may give birth to on-line access to users at the point requested. Some institutions have also engaged in VSAT connections and other radio transmission for the same purpose,

In recent time, the use of Internet has become so prominent in the drive for making Information and data transfers available to its users. Consequently, the need for Internet has become imminent to meet the fast growing population and the challenges posed to Internet connections, its working ability and how it can be accessed for the purpose of research motives in various institutions.

Internet has a lot of functions and benefits that are prominent, which can be of immense use to various educational sectors particularly research institutions. Once a user/researcher is connected to the Internet, such a researcher can link tip with any part of the country for the

purpose in which the researcher intends. In the time past, and up to now, there are various misconceptions of what Internet is and what it can do. It is against this background that the clarifications of Internet feature(s) becomes necessary in order to clear the air about Internet erroneous impression.

Many occasionally observe the features of Internet as being wrongly labelled. Internet is described as the total nature of the global inter connection of computers that comprises of a wide range of tools which enable the Internet users to identify the features or tools to denote the function it can perform. For instance, E-mail and world wide websites (www) are very potent tools among others which can be used in combinations to facilitate significant benefit to various operations not only in terms of accuracy and precision but to data accessibility and enhancement of research work which can be provided for necessary and relevant needs in order to manage the various data base.

Internet in most institutions serve as motivating factor to various institutions through which the possibility of using computer as means of transmission, acquisition, processing and dissemination of information to various research interest groups. In most parts of advanced countries, Great Britain, United State of America, Germany and others had achieved a great stride via internet connectivity as medium of reaching out to the clientele or researchers at various locations and providing value added services that will ease research interest in various human endeavours. Similarly, internet is also used as a medium of expression to educate the learners and provide information needs at the door steps to ensure hitch free and cross reference data to the appropriate location.

Internet as a new technology evolution is not only to provide efficient services locally or internationally but also to create socio-cultural awareness among the various research groups. Essentially, there is no iota of doubt that improved data transmission facilities will go along way to reduce the incessant hardship in information acquisitions and data-generation which will serve as basis for research improvements and recognition. In this regard, an urgent call is now made to all heads of institutions to take a bold step in establishing computer technology departments as a way out of technological backwardness. Hence, technology must be embraced as culture at various levels of our institutions. This therefore becomes necessary and imperative to managers, administrators, policy makers and information practitioners to adopt the use of computers in all segments of our societies.

In spite of the outcry of the advanced nations of the world for computer operation, there is still a conservative approach of Some Institutions participating in computer technology towards the new emerging technologies. The opinion expressed in some quarters is of what become the end of technologist is more pigmentation of no substance because computer technologies has no alternative to information accuracy, fastness and reliability coupled with full proved approach.

PROSPECTS OF INTERNET TO RESEARCH

WORKS

In some parts of the world today, particularly Europe, Germany and even Asia there has been an intuition towards the appreciation of information technology as a medium of information acquisition and data retrieval for research developments and growth. The on-line and off-lines batches are provided via Internet connectivity from any location and access information.

Information technology via Internet can reduce hardship in data generation and processing of information, while it can also locate information on the Internet where there is specific information stored to access and present in a more logical way.

Besides, the use of Internet will afford the users the opportunity of flexibility and interaction between the researchers with the owner of the website and consequently help researchers through Internet access from any part of the country database's connection. As the internet grows towards becoming a standard for information access retrieval and exchange have occurred like a "safe in the emerging technologies, this will stimulate the necessary policies and research into possible use of technology. Over the years, information exchange have revealed that information technology is a medium of expression and retrieval purposes. Internet is of significance especially in the areas of production acceleration and efficiency of research works through the adequate provision, enabling environment and conclusive climate.

In addition the problem of technological transfer cannot only be reduced to the nearest minimum but also afforded through Internet connectivity. This is not all, the issue of time factor of information precision and accuracy of data generation with data genuity are guaranteed through Internet operation. Essentially research works becomes less burdensome, more authentic and functional as a result of information reliability.

CONCLUSIONS

The constraints of various institutions of learning are identified while the educational advancement is fragile with the support of infrastructural facilities that is grossly inadequate. This factor has been largely responsible for the existing weak technological base. Consequently, technology has remained an imported phenomenon that will continue to depend on the availability of foreign experts for its survival.

Besides, the purchasing ability of the Nigerian currency is dwindling daily and restricts the users' ability to import and access to modern technology. More so, the incessant NEPA failure and irregularity in the functioning of telecommunication facilities have not supported the level of sustaining the expected technological development.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Envicb, N. (1977). *Quantity Control & Reliability*. 45 Ed. New York, Individual Press.

Ezeano, V. (1992). Computer and ethnics: *Computer Journal of African Research*. Vol. 3, No. 13 pp. 124.

Olatunde, 3. (1999). The role of technology. *The Journal of Nigerian Bankers*, No. 1, Vol. 2 pg. 15-18.

Owode, M. (1991). *Computer Science and its Curriculum*, National Board for Technical Education Vol. 1 No. 5 pg. 121.

Nigeria Journal of Emotional Psychology and Sport Ethics Vol 4, 2000